

Introduction

Nanotechnology opens new prospects in the fight against trypanosomatids, a group of protozoans responsible for diseases such as African trypanosomiasis, Chagas disease, and leishmaniasis. From the perspective of advancing experimental research, it is interesting to analyze the most popular directions of nanotechnological developments aimed at addressing the medical, economic, and social problems associated with these diseases. This study aimed to analyze scientific research data on the use of nanoparticles to combat trypanosomatids, which pose threats to both humans and animals. The data analysis was performed by using the databases DOAJ, Scopus, ScienceDirect, PubMed.

Results

Analysis of literature data reveals that since 2006, scientific research in this area has progressed in seven main directions:

Much of the work involves the development of nanoscale drug delivery systems that target trypanosomatid parasites with minimal toxicity to host cells (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Nanoparticles employed to grapple anti-leishmanials associated drawbacks (doi.org/10.1186/s12951-021-00853-0).

Secondly, studies are exploring the possibility of creating nanoparticles encapsulating drugs, thereby significantly increasing their stability and bioavailability.

Thirdly, some research focuses on the creation of nanoparticles encapsulating multiple drugs, with their synergistic effect aiding in overcoming resistance mechanisms.

Fourthly, diagnostic tools are being developed with nanoparticle-based biosensors, enabling sensitive detection of specific trypanosomatid biomarkers or genetic sequences (figure 2).

Figure 2. A representation of the various functionalization moieties for nanosystems utilized for the detection of biomolecules in diagnostics (doi.org/10.3390/nano13071247).

Research trends and emerging topics.

(A) Trypanosomatid research topics represented in the set of HC articles
(B) The violin plot shows those topics for which the HC articles have a median publication date later than 2010
(doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0010040.g005>, doi.org/10.3390/diseases11040153.)

The fifth direction involves theranostics: nanoparticles combining therapeutic and diagnostic capabilities on a single platform, allowing personalized treatment strategies and monitoring of treatment response.

A sixth group of studies explores vector control strategies to reduce the transmission of trypanosomatids, with the development of nanoparticle-based insecticides or repellents targeting tsetse flies or triatomine bugs.

The seventh direction focuses on developing nanovaccines that mimic the structure of trypanosomatid parasites, effectively training the immune system to recognize and mount a reliable response against them.

Noteworthy is the simplification of monitoring the toxicity nanoparticles for combatting neglected tropical diseases using instrumental proteomics, genomics, and metabolomics methods. A multi-omics experimental approach is considered an optimal strategy for searching for effective nanoparticles and assessing their nanotoxicity.

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